

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING LATIN IN PHARMACEUTICAL UNIVERSITIES

Matyusupova Shakarjon Begmamatovna

Senior teacher of Latin at the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature of the Tashkent
Pharmaceutical Institute

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Abstract. *The article talks about teaching Latin in pharmaceutical universities. Even now in the modern world, in which it is already possible to rely on artificial intelligence, extensive literature in the world of science, the basics of scientific and cultural terminology, almost all areas of human activity are still in Latin. The Latin language serves as the main source of continuing education and enrichment and a growing international socio-political and scientific terminology in almost all fields of science and technology. Therefore, knowledge of Latin for a doctor allows you to understand the terminology of other related sciences. Learning Latin improves a doctor's vocabulary and facilitates the process of memorizing new words of foreign origin. Students are introduced to special concepts in Latin from the earliest stages of medical science. Derivative in medicine is traditionally used as an international terminology in anatomy and pharmacology, as well as in the preparation of recipes. Knowledge of Latin allows doctors from different countries to easily understand each other. With a long tradition of using Latin in medicine, it serves as a unifying factor to unite physicians and medical education throughout the world.*

Keywords: *latin, medicine, doctor, terminology, pharmaceutical terminology, science and technology.*

Introduction: The 21st century is a turbulent time characterized by unprecedented global changes and transformations. Achievements of science and the development of technology are acquiring more advanced forms every year, giving new impetus to mental processes as new opportunities and means emerge for transforming and connecting external awareness of the surrounding reality with internal processes of mental activity [1]. As we enter the age of digital and information communication technologies, we are faced with challenges of a type that we have never encountered before. Teachers in higher education institutions around the world are trying to keep up with technological progress, but in order to prepare students for life in the 21st century, it is necessary to reconsider the entire education system as a whole and take a fresh look at teaching methods [2–3]. To optimize and achieve maximum efficiency of the educational process, it is necessary to clearly understand the true needs of students of the 21st century, namely:

- effectively convey information, thoughts and feelings to other people;
- take a creative approach to solving emerging problems and issues;
- actively interact with other people;
- think critically, compare and analyze.

Modern students need teaching methods and techniques that could optimize the effectiveness of the entire educational process. Today, the learning process is no longer limited to the traditional blackboard for writing down facts, dates, examples, formulas and the teacher's lecture, which are perceived as something boring, outdated and uninteresting. Thanks to developing technologies, active knowledge of the surrounding reality occurs in geometric progression [4]. Currently, whether we like it or not, we all live in an information society. At the

same time, the opportunities that are now opening up are used very poorly. Our task is to “unfold” the information society towards the needs that people who live in our country have.

First of all, among young people receiving education, scientists, researchers, teachers, educators. We must teach people from childhood and at all stages of the educational process not to be afraid of this information, teach them to use it, work with it and manage it correctly.

Pharmaceutical terminology includes terms from special disciplines that study the production and use of medicines of plant, mineral, animal and synthetic origin. The basis of the term pharmaceutical, like many other pharmaceutical concepts (pharmaceutics, pharmacognosy, pharmacology, phytopharmacy, etc.) is the ancient Greek noun *phármakon* [faarmakon] - medicine. Historically, the ancient Greek and Latin languages played a key role in the formation and development of European pharmaceutical terminology, and even today, a future pharmacist or pharmacist cannot do without studying the basics of pharmaceutical Latin. To understand the reasons for this fact, it is necessary to turn to the origins of medicine. The founders of medical science were the ancient Greeks, who, thanks to their unique talent, laid the foundations of almost all sciences and arts - mathematics, physics, biology, history, philosophy, philology, poetry, theater, etc., as evidenced by the very names of these sciences and arts.

Medicine has historically had a Latin name (*medicina*), but Greek names denoting treatment and the ability to heal (*iatreía*, *therapia*) also entered the European lexicon (cf. Russian: therapy, pharmacotherapy, pediatrics, psychiatry, etc.). Hippocrates is considered the “father” of scientific European medicine. In his works, which have partially survived to our time, the foundations of scientific medical terminology were laid. In the time of Hippocrates, as throughout antiquity, there was no independent science about medicines and their use - the doctor and the pharmacist acted as one person, each doctor himself or with the help of his students was engaged in the manufacture of medicines. It is known that Hippocrates had a special work on this topic called “*Ta phármaka*” (medicines), which has not survived. In his surviving works, Hippocrates uses the word *pharmakeía* (Latinized as *pharmacía*) to refer to the art of preparing medicine. In these same works there is a lot of information about the manufacture of various medicines, in particular, they mention the names of about 235 medicinal plants. The names of many plants go back to the works of such famous ancient Greek scientists as Theophrastus, who was a student of Aristotle. Of his numerous works, the essay “*On the History of Plants*” in 10 books has survived. The scientist Dioscorides described more than 400 plants in his works. His work “*On Medicinal Substances*” has been preserved. The most significant physician and pharmacist after Hippocrates was the Greek Claudius Galen, who was from Pergamum in Asia Minor, but lived and worked in Rome. Galen was the author of numerous works in Greek, much of which has survived.

The need to study Latin in pharmaceutical universities depends on the following circumstances:

For more than one and a half thousand years, Latin has been the language of medicine and pharmaceuticals. Based on extensive scientific literature in Latin (historical, philological, scientific, philosophical and religious treatises) the fundamentals of scientific and cultural terminology are put into practice in all spheres of human activity.

And at present, Latin serves as the main language, a source of education and replenishment of the constantly and growing international socio-political and scientific terminology in almost all areas of science and technology. Thus, knowledge of Latin for an employee of medicine and pharmacology, pharmaceutics gives the ability to understand other, related terminology of

sciences. And the case that is most interesting in our age is that discoveries occur at the intersection of sciences, which represent a very important advantage for obtaining information about them and the practical application of the results of discoveries in medical science and practice. Latin is the language of all Anglo-Saxon languages without exception (French, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian, German, English and others) descended from the Latin language or borrowed many things. For example, in French, Italian, Spanish, and Romanian, 89% of words are of Latin origin. 65% in English, German. Therefore, learning Latin will improve the vocabulary of a doctor, pharmacologist, pharmacist and facilitate the process of memorizing new words of foreign origin. And nowadays Latin is an indispensable attribute of the modern world. Latin expressions and idioms, proverbs, sayings, quotes (in Latin or in translation) today, in the 21st century, are in constant demand, not only interesting and necessary ancient proverbs, as well as idiomatic expressions, allow a deeper, more accurate perception of the essence of the data obtained. They are used in documentation by official international organizations, special disciplines in medical terminology, veterinary medicine, pharmacology, and in speeches by lawyers. They are also used in fiction, theater and cinema. People often use Latin without even realizing it. Many Latin words have taken root in modern word languages and common and widespread and long-existing Latin expressions have developed into catchphrases. They are even called "winged Latin". One of the most important disciplines in the training of future specialists in the field of medicine is undoubtedly Latin.

Special concepts in Latin students are encouraged from the earliest stages of medical science. These are, first of all, the names of organs and parts of the body, chemical compounds and medications, diseases and methods of treating them, and much more. The phrases are called medical terms and they are a collection of medical terminology. Indeed, the Latin language that lies in it to this day not only gives special importance to its study, as the language of one of the most ancient cultures, but also as a language that medical professionals need in practical activities. Latin also better helps students understand other languages with significant vocabularies; since it is saturated with words of Latin origin, it has become internationalism, that is, with words whose appearance and partial (or complete) expressions of meanings and concepts are international in nature. In medicine, Latin is traditionally used as an international terminology for anatomy and pharmacology and also in the preparation of recipes. Knowledge of Latin allows doctors from different countries to easily understand each other. The long tradition of using Latin in medicine serves as a unifying factor for physicians around the world and for the integration of medical education. Because scientific medical terminology is an international dictionary in many respects built on Latin and its forms, then it is equally understandable and convenient for doctors all over the world. Therefore, studying Latin and maintaining a high level of knowledge in this area is a very urgent task of modern education.

The same goes for drug names. In this area it is especially important to unite, because then it is impossible to move in the endless sea of medicine. Recipes were written a long time ago in Latin and according to certain rules, so for example, a recipe given in other countries. The study of Latin in medical school reveals the way in which students consciously master and become literate in the use of constantly updated medical care terminology - the professional language of the future medical specialty. The basics of mastering medicine, terminology in Latin should include in initial courses through practical training elements of grammar and principles of word formation, as well as the meaning of Latin word formation, elements and a certain minimum of

terminology dictionary. Work with training and specialty in subsequent courses helps students know the terms of Latin origin and elements of Latin grammar in literature in many disciplines, both in their native language and in foreign languages. Therefore, the need for the study and knowledge of Latin in pharmaceutical universities is undeniable; elements of Latin are necessary for future pharmacists or pharmacologists for the successful development of their specialty and literacy in the use of professional language in the future.

Conclusion: Thus, it is impossible to derive derivative bases without medical education. The study of Latin is of great importance in the training of specialists, because it contributes to the conscious assimilation and understanding of medical terms of Latin origin, who he meets and what his practical activities use. Doctors from ancient times such Latin proverbs are known during the times: *Invia est in sine lingua Latina* through medicine (it is impossible to pass in medicine without Latin). This statement also applies to our times. And it needs to be applied in practice, defining the study of Latin as a mandatory element of the state educational standard.

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